

Table 1: Extended discussion of challenges and comparison on how they are addressed by the proposed architecture and other proposals

ID	Challenge name	Challenge description	Challenge addressing	Architectural modules involved	Technical proposals addressing the challenge	Modules from [3] addressing the challenge
1	Data Consumption and Provision	HDTs face the challenge of integrating data from multiple sources and formats uniformly.	Our solution includes flexible interfaces that are capable of capturing data from internal sensors and external services, ensuring seamless data integration. Additionally, we provide specialized interfaces to supply HDT-generated data to external systems. This dual approach ensures that data flows smoothly both into and out of the HDT, enhancing the overall data ecosystem.	<i>Sensor data consumption, External data consumption, Historical data storage, Historical data interface, Prediction and inference interface</i>	APIs and SDKs [1], [4] solve challenge 1 because they allow us, on the one hand, to implement the consumption of sensor information with a unified interface, so that data can be consumed from HDTs in an abstract way, without going into how it is obtained from the original source; and on the other hand, to offer a different unified interface so that HDT data can be accessed either by external systems or between HDT contexts. The historical data storage leverages databases such as TimescaleDB or ArangoDB for time series management, as they support a wide variety of data types.	The challenge is addressed. An API gateway and a device-to-cloud communication handler allows the HDT to consume data and store it in data lakes. To consume this data, other systems must be integrated in the HDT as microservices.

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2	User-managed Privacy and Security	It is essential that users have full control over the data stored, processed, and managed by their HDT. User-friendly systems must be in place to ensure an average user can understand and use the control mechanisms effectively, expressing their desired control policies.	Our architecture addresses this need through access control protocols that include user-defined access control and user-defined model privileges, allowing users to specify who can access specific data and under what conditions. By empowering users with the ability to manage their own data access and models, we ensure the standards of privacy and security for personal information.	<i>User-defined model privilege control, User-defined access control</i>	PADEC [1] addresses challenge 2 by offering a robust and flexible framework that allows users of HDTs to define detailed access control rules over their resources, predictions, and data from other HDTs, EDTs and external data consumers. Users can assign different levels of granularity to each rule, which means they can decide precisely which data or predictions can be accessed by whom and under what circumstances. PADEC fits the mental model of users, and allows an average user to understand the granularity of data provided and under which circumstances, allowing them to express their personal privacy policies.	The challenge is not addressed. Access control is decided by an administrator.

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3	Support for Multiple Inferential Systems and Predictions	HDTs must be able to integrate and use various types of inferential systems and prediction models, including hybrid and combined approaches.	Our proposal allows the deployment of different inference and prediction models to suit different contexts and needs, and allows for continuous improvement of the collected data. Furthermore, as mentioned above, users have control over the deployment and configuration of these models, ensuring adequate customization according to individual preferences and specific usage conditions.	<i>Historical data analysis, Continuous improvement, Prediction and inference</i>	The approach based on Federated Learning [5] addresses challenge 3, offering several advantages for customizing and continuously improving prediction models in HDTs. This solution allows for the generation, personalization, and updating of individual models, progressively adapting to each user's specific behaviors while preserving privacy by avoiding data centralization. Moreover, its collaborative nature enables the creation of a general model that leverages previous knowledge, which is especially beneficial for new users. Model ensemble techniques are also proposed by combining multiple individual models to improve overall system performance. Each model contributes its strengths, and by working together, can compensate for the weaknesses of the others [6].	The challenge is addressed. An AI/ML framework is provided to perform training and inference over the stored data.

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4	Interoperability with Other Systems	It is crucial that HDTs can interoperate with other systems, facilitating information exchange and collaboration between different HDTs and other systems.	Our solution includes components that specifically enable the consumption and provision of data to and from external sources and other DTs. This promotes interoperability and collaborative development by ensuring that HDTs can effectively communicate and work alongside various systems and entities.	<i>Historical data interface, Prediction and inference interface, Integration</i>	Human Microservices [4] provide the ability to implement and deploy microservices that handle personal user data or other relevant information. This approach allows for the seamless integration of services, creating unified interfaces that facilitate easier and more efficient communication between different HDTs. By leveraging this approach, the data can be consumed and exchanged smoothly between HDTs and external systems, much like how APIs and SDKs allow for straightforward data collection and interaction, addressing the challenge 4.	The challenge is partially addressed. An API gateway allows the HDT to provide and consume data from HDTs and external services. However, data is not provided to external systems, only to internal microservices.

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5	Distributed Deployment in the Computing Continuum.	HDTs must be capable of being deployed in a distributed manner, adapting to different domains and locations throughout the Computing Continuum.	The proposed architecture incorporates a synchronization interface that ensures consistency and updates information between different HDT instances, and an integration module to ensure they can be accessed regardless of their location. These modules facilitate scalable storage and processing, enabling HDTs to operate efficiently across various deployment contexts.	<i>Synchronization interface, Integration</i>	Human Microservices [4] enable the simple implementation and deployment of services across the continuum, including smartphones, addressing practically the challenge 5. This approach includes a well-defined deployment process, where a single microservice definition can be used to implement and deploy multiple instances. This significantly enhances code reuse and reduces development time, making it easier to adapt and scale across different platforms and devices.	The challenge is partially addressed. Microservices from the HDT can be executed at the edge, but multiple instances are not allowed.

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6	Unified View of the Human across Domains.	It is essential that an HDT provides a coherent and unified view of the human, regardless of the existence of domain-specific HDTs or their deployment across the Computing Continuum.	Our solution facilitates the linkage and unification of knowledge between HDTs from different domains, ensuring a comprehensive and unified representation of the user in all contexts.	<i>Human Digital Twin linkage, Integration</i>	Perses [2] addresses challenge 6 by enabling the creation of virtual scenarios involving multiple devices, such as smartphones. This capability allows for the generation of near-real scenarios, providing a comprehensive view of the various HDTs in operation. By simulating interactions across these devices, Perses helps create environments that closely mimic real-world conditions, offering valuable insights into the functionality and interoperability of HDTs in different contexts.	The challenge is not addressed. The HDT considers only the mobility context.

References

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